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Using ice-ocean environment from GECCO reanalysis into Bellhop to better understand sound propagation in the Fram Strait

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As a part of the UNDER-ICE experiment, acoustic signals were sent from a fixed position (600m under the water surface) west of Svalbard across the Fram Strait to a vertical receiver array on a mooring 200 km away. The UNDER-ICE experiment was set up to transmit for two years. The ice conditions along the section varied between partially to fully ice-covered fields according to the ice conditions throughout the 2-year experiment. However, after the experiment, it was found that the signals from the sources were only received in shorter periods during the experiment. In this paper, we investigate several physical characteristics that may be related to the lack of received signals, such as the environmental conditions (e.g., sea ice or oceanographic fronts) and the changes in the source depths during the experiment. In this work, we use the ice-ocean fields from a model reanalysis covering the experimental period. The reanalysis field is compared to oceanographic data obtained during the initial phase of the experiment. The Bellhop model is used to simulate the transmission of acoustic signals using ice-ocean fields from the reanalysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the decline of the Arctic sea ice in recent decades, the sea ice field is transitioning to a more dynamic state containing younger and thinner ice. This influences the acoustic propagation and the natural sources of sound in the central Arctic (e.g., Worcester et al. 2021). In many ways, a steadily increasing part of the central Arctic transfers to become more similar to dynamics and gradients previously only observed in the marginal ice zone (MIZ). Therefore, the MIZ can be seen as a place to study the dynamics and the acoustic environment that will become more normal in the central Arctic.

The geographical area in this work is the MIZ in the Fram Strait. The Fram strait, between Svalbard and Greenland, is the main gateway for water exchange between the Atlantic Ocean and the eastern part of the Arctic Ocean. The strait is a climatic chokepoint for the Arctic Ocean and essential for the ocean heat budget in the Arctic Ocean. Warm water flows northward along the coast of Spitsbergen, turns east North of Svalbard, and brings Atlantic water into the Arctic Basin. In the western part of the Fram Strait, cold and “fresh” water is brought out of the Arctic Basin along the coast of Greenland into the Nordic Seas and the Atlantic Ocean. Therefore, the east of the Fram strait is open water while the west of Fram strait is commonly dominated by more or less dense fields of drifting sea ice. The location of the MIZ varies with seasons and is therefore also referred to as the seasonal ice zone.

Due to the very complex and dynamic oceanography, many short-term and long-term acoustic experiments were carried out in the 1980s and 1990s. The experiments were designed to investigate the ice-ocean processes, ambient noise (e.g., Johannessen et al., 2003), and acoustic propagation (e.g., Dyer et al., 1987, Dahl et al., 1998), including a year-long Greenland Sea tomography experiment 1988-1989. These previous studies showed that the acoustic characteristics are affected by the strong horizontal and vertical variability in the MIZ and the strong temporal variability. After the end of the cold war, there was a long break in acoustic experiments in the Arctic. From 2008 to 2016, a number of tomographic experiments and communication experiments were carried out in the Fram Strait (e.g., Sagen et al. 2017, Hope et al., 2017).

The reflection and scattering due to the rough elastic surfaces are considered as the main difficulty in modeling sound propagation in ice-covered regions. Therefore, the inclusion of reflection and scattering have been a central topic in many polar acoustic studies. Alexander et al. (2013) used the Bellhop model (Porter, 2011) to investigate the propagation losses of 10kHz acoustic signal generated at 20 m depth over a distance of 20 km. Hope et al. (2017) simulated the acoustic propagation at 900 Hz in the Fram Strait using the OASES model. The simulations were compared to observed receptions of signals sent from the icebreaker KV Svalbard as it was moving away from the receiver unit. Their study showed that the acoustic propagation at 900 Hz primarily depends on the sea ice roughness rather than other elastic parameters. Collins et al. (2019) used the parabolic equation method and experimental acoustic data from the Canada Basin Acoustic Propagation Experiment to investigate the capability to model the acoustic propagation in a large-scale ocean environment with gradual horizontal variations in ice-ocean parameters. As a result of their work, they developed an improved method for including range-dependent ice thickness into the parabolic equation for simulations at frequencies below a couple of hundred Hz. Ivakin et al. (2020) used the elastic parabolic equation method for echo sounders at much higher frequencies to quantitatively analyze and explain the time dependence of low- and mid-frequency transmission loss to develop a wide-area synoptic assessment of ice type distribution.

In this paper, we will address the UNDER-ICE acoustic tomography experiment that took place in 2014-2016 in the central part of the Fram Strait (Fig.1) (Storheim et al. (2018, 2020)). In this experiment, a tomographic network of five acoustic moorings was deployed; two of them carried acoustic sweeper sources (200-300 Hz). All five moorings had 100 m long receiver arrays with 10 synchronized self-contained hydrophone modules (see Storheim et al., 2021). After recovery, it was found that one of the sources stopped working after 5 months due to technical failure. Signals from the other source were received in shorter and longer periods until the recordings stopped in February 2016. Based on this situation, we have investigated if the environmental conditions or mooring motion could prevent the acoustic signal from being detected at the receiver array 192 km away from the source. Selected physical parameters that could be related to the failure of receiving signals have been investigated, e.g., sea ice, oceanographic fronts or mooring motion. To carry out the study, we use an ice-ocean reanalysis prepared for the INTAROS project (Lyu et al., 2021) as input to the Bellhop model (Porter, 2011).

2. OBSERVATIONS AND MODELS

A. OBSERVING THE FRAM STRAIT

Extensive work has been done on observing and modeling cold and warm water transports through the Fram Strait, but the work is challenging because of the complex circulation in the strait. The warmer and northbound West Spitsbergen current interacts with the southbound fresher and colder East Greenland Current. A monitoring system consisting of 14-17 oceanographic moorings has been operated since 1996 (Appen et al., 2016), but the moorings could not resolve and account for the mesoscale features or the significant re-circulation in the estimation of the transports through the strait.

Furthermore, ocean modeling systems also struggle to provide realistic simulations of the very complex circulation pattern in the strait. This was the rationale for setting up tomographic systems and to combine the mean averaged measurements of sound speed/ocean temperature with ice-ocean modeling systems through assimilation (Sagen et al., 2017 and Geyer et al., 2019), which started in the DAMOCLES and ACOBAR projects and continued in the UNDER-ICE project. Figure 1 shows the location of the experiments from these three projects.

Figure 1. Map of moorings configuration during the UNDER-ICE (2014-2016), ACOBAR (2010-2012), and DAMOCLES 2008-2009).

B. THE UNDER-ICE EXPERIMENT

The details of the UNDER-ICE field experiment are described in Storheim et al. (2018, 2021). The two acoustic sources (UI-2 and UI-5) were programmed to transmit signals every 8 hours for two years. The signals were received at four 100 m long vertical receiver moorings, each equipped with 10 hydrophones. The experiment was designed to give signal propagation along 8 tracks, indicated by the red lines in Fig.1. After the experiment was completed and the data analysis was progressing, it was found that the signals from UI-5 disappeared and reappeared several times at the receiver moorings during the 2-year experiment. We found this intriguing and started to investigate if the environmental conditions were causing the temporary disappearance of the signals. In this paper, we focus on the receptions of signals from UI-5 obtained at UI-4. We assumed that the source at UI-5 worked during the whole experiment, and we investigated if the missing receptions could be explained by: 1) change in source depth due to mooring motion; 2) the ice conditions; or 3) changes in the oceanographic fields.

The motion of each mooring was monitored throughout the experiment, showing that the source at UI-5 dived by about 200 m, while the UI-4 receiver mooring dived by only a couple of meters.

Oceanographic profiles from CTD/XBT data along the track were available at the beginning and end of the experiment. The oceanographic sections showed that the typical strong vertical stratification was present under the ice-covered western side of the strait. The relatively cold and fresh water near the surface was overlaying the warmer water masses below, but this layer disappeared when moving into the ice-free area. This transition zone is related to the location of the MIZ (e.g., Johannessen et al., 2003). Sea ice observations from satellites were

available daily, while XBT profiles along the track were only obtained at the beginning and end of the experiment. Other oceanographic data were not obtained along the section during the experiment.

C. ICE-OCEAN RE-ANALYSIS

Since few oceanographic data were available along the track, a 4D ocean state reanalysis was used to obtain information about the changes in oceanographic conditions during the experiment. The reanalysis is based on the GECCO model using the 4DVAR assimilation of sea ice from remote sensing, ocean data from moorings and buoys (Lyu et al., 2021). This reanalysis was done under the INTAROS project. Atmospheric forcing fields were from the 6-hourly National Centers for Environmental Prediction reanalysis 1 (NCEP-RA1) (Kalnay et al., 1996), including 2-m air temperature, 10-m wind vectors, precipitation rate, 2-m specific humidity, downward longwave radiation, and net shortwave radiation, as well as computed surface momentum, heat, and freshwater fluxes. The reanalysis provided ocean state estimates on a grid represented by 50 vertical z-levels ranging from 10 m at the surface to 456 m in the deep ocean. In the horizontal, a curvilinear grid with a resolution of ~ 16 km was used. Prior to the acoustic modeling, the oceanographic fields were interpolated to a curvilinear grid with a resolution of ~ 2 km.

D. ACOUSTIC MODEL

The Bellhop model is an acoustic numerical model based on the ray theory (Porter, 2011). The model is computationally efficient and has intuitive physical meaning for wide applications. The model has a module that can add range independent sea ice reflection coefficient to calculate sound propagation in the ice-covered regions. However, the range-dependent sea ice conditions characterizing the MIZ are not included in the Bellhop model. In this study, we used a model with a modified sea ice module to simulate acoustic propagation under range dependent sea ice ranging from open ocean to fully ice covered. Time series of the interpolated oceanographic fields were used in the Bellhop model as well as sea ice information along the track.

In the modified model, each ray is tagged with information on where it hits the sea-ice interface and at what incidence angle. The horizontal distance from the sound source, gives the ice thickness from the reanalysis. This ice thickness and incidence angle were used to search for corresponding reflection coefficient for calculation of reflection loss in the Bellhop model. Thus, the range dependent sea ice characteristics (thickness, etc.) were included. Therefore, the modified Bellhop model can be used in MIZ.

3. VERIFICATION OF THE RE-ANALYSIS FOR USE IN THE ACOUSTIC SIMULATIONS.

The sound speed section from the reanalysis data was compared with XBT/CTD sound speed data to verify the use of reanalysis as input to the acoustic model in Fig.2. Panel (a) shows the sound speed derived from the XBT/CTD data obtained between UI-5 and UI-4 during deployment in 2014. Data from 21 profiles were interpolated onto a grid with a resolution of 1 km in range and 10 m in depth. It can be clearly seen from these observations that there is a layer with a sound speed of less than 1450 m/s caused by cold and less saline water near the surface between the moorings. The thickness of the low sound speed layer varies from 10 m to 180 m (the surface duct, red line). There is another minimum in sound speed near 800 m (purple line), forming the axis of a deep sound speed channel. The depth of this sound speed minimum rises along the section towards UI-4. Hence the area typically has a strong shallow sound speed channel and a weaker deep sound speed channel with stronger horizontal variability.

In panel (b), the section of ocean sound speed was obtained from the reanalysis data from the time of deployment, 11-12 September 2014. A total of 101 profiles were obtained with ~ 2 km horizontal separation and values at 44 depths. The profiles were interpolated to the same grid as the observations in panel (a). The shallow sound speed channel is marked by the dashed red line in panel (b). The deep sound channel is still observed but with less variability compared to observations (panel (a)). The cold-water layer coincides with the presence of sea ice and disappears near the source area where there is no ice. The deep sound channel rises from 1100 m in the western part to 300 m in the eastern part of the section. The change in sound channel depth is mostly dependent on the ocean environment and the presence of sea ice. Panel (c) shows that the sound speed from the reanalysis is generally larger than from the XBT/CTD data. The largest differences are found within the upper 50 m between 40 km and 100 km, where the model does not show the same extension of the surface duct as the observations.

Figure 2. Profiles and sections of ocean sound speed between UI-5 and UI-4 obtained on 11-12 September 2014, where the bottom is shown in brown. The red dashed line is the surface duct, and the purple dashed line is the deep sound channel. (a) is from the XBT/CTD data. (b) is from the GECCO reanalysis and (c) is the difference between (a) and (b). The profiles to the left are range-averaged sound speed for (a), (b) and (c), respectively.

The model produces realistic ice cover because it assimilates sea ice concentration from satellite data, which are quite accurate on scales larger than 10 km. Since the sea ice influences the upper ocean, we can expect that the model is also quite realistic just under the ice. However, the ice edge position can change quickly, and it can be difficult to correlate with the oceanographic conditions under the sea ice. For example, when the XBT data were collected, the ice was covering the whole section, and the surface duct was observed across the section. However, during the same time period, the ice was only covering half the section in the reanalysis. The surface duct is only observed in the western half of the track. The distribution of sound speed in the model is generally in agreement with observations, but as expected, there are differences in the upper ocean where the fronts and mesoscale activities take place. Furthermore, the front and horizontal gradients in the upper 1000 m in the reanalysis are much weaker than in the observed data. The reanalysis assimilates very few oceanographic profiles in this region, and therefore, it is the physics of the model that decides the ocean conditions under the ice, and full agreement with data is not to be expected. In addition, the resolution of the model is too coarse to pick up all the processes (e.g., eddies and fronts), correctly.

There is a reasonably good agreement between the reanalysis and observation in the deeper part of the ocean, and the model can represent realistic phenomena such as surface ducts and other gradients in the shallower layers. Based on this the reanalysis fields will be our ocean – laboratory and used to provide sea ice information and oceanographic fields as input to the acoustic model.

4. ACOUSTIC PROPAGATION IN THE MIZ.

Four days (12.09.2014, 06.09.2015, 15.01.2016, 15.05.2016) were selected to investigate sound propagation in more detail under different ice-ocean conditions. Maps of ice extent and thickness from the reanalysis are shown in Fig. 3 for the selected dates, showing that the ice conditions between UI-5 and UI-4 varied significantly during the experiment. Panel (a) shows that most of the area was covered with 1-3 m thick ice, except near the UI-5 mooring. In panel (b), nearly one year after (a), the ice-cover was thinner than 1 m. In panel (c) the thickness had grown significantly in the western part from September 2015 to January 2016, whereas more of the eastern part became ice-free. In panel (d) UI-5 was embedded in sea ice and the whole section was covered by ice with thickness from 1 m to 3 m.

Subsequently, we used the Bellhop model to simulate the sound propagation for the selected days. The parameters used in the Bellhop model are given in Table 1.

Figure 3. Maps of sea ice thickness distribution from GECCO reanalysis on the four selected days. The red stars show the locations of UI-5 and UI-4. The black dots mark the positions of XBT/CTD data.

Table 1. The Bellhop model Inputs.

Parameter	Value	
Environment		
Frequency	250	Hz
Range	200	km
Environment depth	3.5	km
Transmission loss	coherent	
Bottom surface	acoustic half-space	
Source		
Source depth	600	m
Start Angle (from horizontal)	-90°	
End Angle (from horizontal)	90°	
No. beams	1,800	
Receivers		
Number horizontal	201	
Number vertical	3501	
Main receiver depth	200	m
Max receiver range	200	km

The segments of sea ice used in the simulations were simplified to flat elastic layers of different ice thickness with no roughness. Furthermore, the sea surface is assumed to be single layer described by the physical parameters shown in Table 1. From this, the reflection coefficients for different ice thicknesses were obtained, and a reflection coefficient file was generated. This file is used as input to the Bellhop model. Ice thickness for each segment along the section was used to select the right reflection coefficient.

Table 2. Sea ice physical parameters.

Parameter	P-wave velocity	S-wave velocity	density	Longitudinal wave absorption [11]	Shear wave absorption [11]
Value	3593.4m/s	1819.8m/s	917kg/m ³	$\alpha = 0.06f$ dB/m	$\beta = 6\alpha$ dB/m

Figure 4 shows the ocean sound speed (SSP) section between UI-5 and UI-4 extracted from the reanalysis for the same days as in Figure 3.

Figure 4. Case studies of SSP between UI-5 and UI-4 on (a) 12.09.2014, (b) 06.09.2015, (c) 15.01.2016, and (d) 15.05.2016. In each panel, the colormap shows the sound speed with the averaged ice thickness on top (the blue area marks ice thickness) and profile of range-averaged sound is shown to the right. The acoustic rays (Angle: -5-5°) from the source at 600 m are marked by thin black lines. The purple dashed lines indicate the deep sound channels, and the red line indicates a surface duct.

It is clearly observed in all panels in Fig. 4 that the depth of the deep sound channel (in purple) is strongly related to the distribution of ice thickness, where it is deeper in open water and shallower in ice areas. It is also seen that each case has different vertical and horizontal gradients in the sound speed in the upper 1000 m with different distribution of rays. This shows that the acoustic propagation is strongly affected by the oceanographic and sea ice conditions in the MIZ.

In panel (a), the sound rays propagating upwards are reflected downwards without reaching the surface because of a 200 m thick layer of higher sound speed underneath the open water. This layer extends 100 km from UI-5 where as it weakens and finally disappears. In the same region the deep sound channel rises very quickly from ~1100 m to ~400 m over 20 km. This allows the rays to reach and interact with the ice cover until they reach UI-4. However, the rays are split into two groups, one penetrating deeper than the other. Both groups reach the surface but at different range intervals.

In Panel b) we observe layer of higher sound speed above the source, but the layer only extends about to 20 km from the source. This layer of higher sound speed prevents the rays from reaching the surface. In this region the deep sound channel rises from ~1300 m to ~600 m, allowing the rays to reach the surface and interact with the ice. The sound speed channel shallows gradually from ~600 to ~400 m as it approaches UI-4.

In panel (c), the deep sound channel rises gradually from UI-5 towards UI-4. Furthermore, a thin layer of lower sound speed overlays a relatively weak plume of high sound speed. The depth and the strength of the core of the plume is gradually reduced into the ice covered region till the plume disappears at 100 km. Some deep rays seem to be undisturbed by the plume of high sound speed. However, quite a few rays are trapped above the

plume till the plume rises and disappears at 100 km. From there these rays start mingling with the deeper going rays.

For panel (d), the sound source depth is situated within the plume of high sound speed. Therefore, the rays can propagate both upwards and downwards, but after once surface reflection they are bent downwards when they pass through this zone. After this all the rays continue as deep going rays, but with no distinct groups. There is a jump of the deep sound channel near 70 km in the range from ~ 1100 m to ~ 400 m, which together with gradients in the upper ocean can cause the rather messy ray pattern.

5. SENSITIVITY TO MOORING MOTION.

The sensitivity of acoustic receptions to varying source depth due to mooring motion is described in this section. In Figure 5, panel (a) shows the time series of source depth variation during the whole experiment. The source dived from 600 m down to a maximum near 800 m below the surface, while the receiver mooring only dived by a few meters (not shown). The varying source depths were used as input to the Bellhop model, together with the corresponding oceanographic fields. Panel (b) shows the time series of arriving rays at different receiver depths and the source depth from (a). Panel (c) shows the number of arrivals using a fixed source depth at 600m. The difference between (b) and (c) is shown in panel (d). It is observed that the variation of source depth between 600-800 has little effect on the number of acoustic arrivals. From this, we conclude that changes in acoustic receptions caused by environmental parameters are much stronger than the impact of varying source depth due to mooring motion. In particular, it is observed that the periods with very few receptions are present both when the source depth is varying and when the source is fixed. Therefore, in the following analysis, we use a fixed source depth at 600 m in the acoustic model.

Figure 5 (a) source depth as a function of time, (b) the number of arrivals at UI-4 using the varying source depths. (c) the number of arrivals at UI-4 using a fixed source depth of 600m, (d) the difference of the number of arrivals between (b) and (c).

6. SENSITIVITY TO ENVIRONMENTAL PARAMETERS.

The time series of the range average sound speed profile between UI-5 and UI-4 is shown in Fig. 6a. The range averages are calculated daily from 01.09.2014 to 31.07.2016 based on the reanalysis. The strength and the thickness of the upper layer of low sound varies with time. The higher sound speed in the deeper water masses

is varies with time. The depth of the minimum sound speed in the upper 200 m is shown in Fig. 6b, while the sea ice extension and thickness is shown in Fig 6c. There is no clear seasonal variability in any of the timeseries. However, the periods with larger extension of the deep sound speed channel (red in b) and the periods with high sound speed in a) seem to correspond. Comparing b) with c) shows that the depth of the deep sound channel partly varies with the ice cover, but that the sea ice variability is more rapid and stronger than the changes in the water masses. The deeper ocean does not adjust quickly to changes in the ice conditions, which is expected.

The daily range dependent sound speed profiles and ice distributions along the track are used as input to the Bellhop model. For each day, the number of arrivals at different receiving depths are calculated for a source depth of 600 m. In the number of arrivals, only the rays with energy above a mean level were calculated using the energy from all the arrived rays. The result of the calculations is shown in Figure 6 d.

The lowest number of receptions occurs in the upper 200 m when the sound rays are trapped in the deep sound channel. The reception is better when the environment allows the sound rays to be trapped in the cold-water layer. The most stable and good receptions are found for receivers between 200~1000m.

Figure 6. Time series of (a) sound speed profile (SSP), (b) depth of minimum sound, (c) sea ice thickness, and (d) the number of arrivals at the receiver depth, all based on input field from the reanalysis. The former three variables are used in the Bellhop model to calculate the arrivals. The black arrows correspond to the dates 12.09.2014, 06.09.2015, 15.01.2016, respectively, which are the same as in Fig. 3 and 4

In figure 6b it is observed how rapidly the depth of the deep sound speed minimum is reduced from around 1400 meters to 400 meters. This indicates the location and strength of the oceanographic (temperature) gradients. It is observed in figure 6 d that the lowest number of arrivals are during periods when the strong gradients happen at short ranges. If, however, this gradient is located at further away from the source e.g. between 50-150 km there are generally more arrivals. For example, the number of arrivals is high during September to November 2014 and from December 2015 to July 2016 this is when the oceanographic gradient is located at ranges of the order of 100 km. While, during August and September in 2015 the oceanographic gradient is only around 25 km away from the source, and the number of arrivals are very low during this period. Based on this we claim that the poor receiving conditions are related to periods when strong oceanographic gradients are located relatively close to the source mooring.

7. CONFIGURATION OF INSTRUMENTS

In this section, we investigate how the receptions can be improved by changing the configuration of the receivers or the source on the moorings. In Fig. 7, the numbers of received rays are calculated and presented as

a function of receiver depths and source depths on the four selected days (same days as in Fig 3 and 4). As in Fig. 6, only rays with energy above a mean level are included. The red (blue) colors indicate higher (lower) efficiency of acoustic energy transmission. The red box illustrates the receiver depths and the variable source depths during the UNDER-ICE experiment.

Figure 7. The number of received rays as a function of receiver depths and source depths on (a) 12.09.2014, (b) 06.09.2015, (c) 15.01.2016, and (d) 15.05.2016. The colors indicate the efficiency of the acoustic energy transmission.

The number of arrivals at all receiver depths in (a), (c), and (d) are higher than in (b) for all the source depths. From this, we conclude that the lowest transmission conditions occur when the shallowing of the deep sound channel is close to the source (Fig 6). Furthermore, we can observe that the number of received rays are more sensitive to the source depth than the receiver depth.

In (a) the strongest signals are found for the deepest receivers (800 m - 1200 m) for source depths shallower than 400 m. For deeper source depths, most of the sound rays are received at shallower receivers between 200 m and 600 m. The situation is the opposite in (c). For shallow source depths, less than 200 m, most of the sound rays are received above 500 m near the surface. For source depths from 200 m and 700 m, most of the rays are received between 500 m and 1200 m. For the source deeper than 700 m, a significant number of sound rays can be received almost at any depth.

In (d) the sound rays are received at all receiver depths considered for source depths shallower than 700 m. For deeper source depths, fewer rays are received at depths shallower than 200 m.

The receiver configuration and the variable source depths used in the experiment are shown by the red rectangle. The number of received rays within this rectangle is rather low and indicates that the configuration was not optimal for the four selected days. In particular, for case b) the number of received rays was low for all source depths and all receiver depths when strong oceanographic gradients were close to the source.

Comparing the four panels in Figure 7, we observe that a change in the configuration of the source and receivers to improve the number of arrivals in most of the cases. The suggested configuration is indicated by the black rectangle, which show a high number of received rays from 200m down to 1200 m for source depths around 500 m for all panels except (b). When the oceanographic front is close to the source, as in (b), there is no optimal solution. In all the other cases, a doubling the length of the receiver array would further improve the experiment significantly.

8. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The Bellhop model with a modified sea ice module has been used to simulate range-dependent acoustic propagation in the MIZ using time series of ice-ocean data from a reanalysis based on GECCO. The main goal of the study was to find out if this particular environment or mooring motion could cause the acoustic receptions to disappear for long periods during the UNDER-ICE experiment. Furthermore, it was a goal to investigate if a better source and receiver configuration could have improved the results of the experiment.

From our study, we can conclude that variable sound source depth due to mooring motion had a minor effect on the reception of the acoustic signal compared to the effect of changing ocean environment.

Furthermore, our study confirms that the oceanographic conditions can make it hard to transmit signal from a source outside the ice edge to a receiver array inside the ice edge for any source/receiver configuration. The worst conditions are if there are strong horizontal gradients in the oceanographic conditions close to the source.

The simulation results show that the configuration of source and receiver array can be optimized to accommodate better receptions in most of the oceanographic conditions considered in our study. Therefore, we suggest modifying the configuration by lowering the receiver array and putting the source at a shallower depth (500 m) in future acoustic experiments in the Fram Strait marginal ice zone.

Our findings have consequences for low frequency communication and underwater geo-positioning (UW-GPS). The sound source used in the UNDER-ICE experiment produced a broadband sweep from 200-300 Hz. A narrow band (1.5 Hz bandwidth) at 250 Hz RAOS signal are used by gliders to navigate and postprocessing for geo-positioning of underwater floats. Therefore, our analysis will be useful for understanding the capability and limitations of gliders and floats to receive signals in a network of acoustic sources in the Marginal Ice Zone e.g. which listening depths will be the optimal and under what conditions will the signal be difficult to receive. The study also provides insight into communication capabilities in the Marginal Ice Zone at frequencies between 200-300 Hz.

In our model study, we used smooth sea ice with variable thickness. The effect of scattering from a rough underside of the ice will make the transmission of signals even more complex. The next step in our study is to study how to include a scattering from the sea ice in our acoustic simulations along with other frequencies.

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